

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report of activities and first update of the
Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
Deliverable D6.2**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

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<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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Abbreviation list

Acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
EW3	ESiWACE3
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High Performance Computing
IPM	Innovation Project Manager
IPMP	Intellectual Property Management Plan
ITC	Inclusiveness Target Countries
METH	Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
PMO	Project Manager Office
PROD	Product (new or improved)
SCI	Scientific discovery, model, theory (...)
SW	Software
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels

Table of contents

1. Abstract/publishable summary	6
2. Conclusion & Results	6
3. Project objectives	6
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	7
4.1. Introduction	7
4.2. Objectives	7
4.3. Target audiences	8
4.4. Planned and completed actions	9
4.4.1. Communication (Task 6.1)	10
4.4.2. Engagement (Tasks 6.2 & 6.3)	11
4.4.3. Dissemination (Task 6.4)	14
4.4.4. Exploitation (Task 6.5)	15
4.5. Feedback	16
5. References	16
6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered	17
7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy	17
8. Sustainability	18
9. Community engagement, dissemination and exploitation	18
9.1 Target audience	18
9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable	18
9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted	20
9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable	20
Appendix 1. Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP)	21
1. Introduction	21
2. Context/legal framework	21
2.1 Treatment of confidential information	22
2.2 Background	22
2.3 Results	22
2.4 Communication/dissemination	23
2.5 Exploitation paths	23
2.6 Third party	24
2.7 Change of membership	24
2.8 Technology Readiness Levels (TRL)	24
2.9 Liability towards each other and dispute resolution	25
3. Action plan	25
3.1 Setting Definitions	25
3.2 Background management	25

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

3.3 Identification of Results	26
3.4 Identification of Exploitation paths	27
4. IP portfolio implementation	27
4.1 Individual results	28
4.2 Joint and Multiple results	36
5. Analysis	41

1. Abstract/publishable summary

This document comprises a first updated version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) for the ESiWACE3 project set out in ESiWACE3 Deliverable 6.1 dated 30/06/2023. It describes the goals and target audiences for communication and dissemination of the project's outcomes, the channels to be used and the actions to be taken. The document also reports on actions already taken in line with the CDEP since Deliverable 6.1 was submitted.

2. Conclusion & Results

The updated CDEP is set out in section 4, which also lists actions taken to date. Further reports and updates of the plan are envisaged for months 36 and 48 of the project.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the GA:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
O4. Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	Yes
O5. Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
O6. Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth System science and HPC, and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Serve as a landing point for the European community of Earth System modellers to cooperate and exchange knowledge and expertise.	Yes
Strong focus on communication and networking activities to broaden the community.	Yes
Particularly addressing early career scientists and female researchers and contacting Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs).	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) provides the context, strategy and intended actions to be taken to facilitate engagement of the project with its target audiences and to ensure that the outcomes of the project are disseminated to those who can benefit from them. It sets out the goals for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, identifies the various audiences and describes the channels that will be used to reach them.

Specifically, the CDEP identifies concrete actions to:

- raise awareness of the project, its objectives, progress and outcomes with interested parties beyond the project's community;
- seek interaction and engagement with selected audiences;
- promote the services, training and tools developed within the project to potential users;
- disseminate the results of research conducted within the project to the wider weather and climate modelling and HPC communities;
- identify the potential for exploitation of the results of the project.

As at the time of writing, month 18 of the project, a variety of activities have already been undertaken. These are also described in this report.

4.2. Objectives

The purpose of the CDEP is to define the strategy for building a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth System modelling across Earth System science and HPC and for establishing connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives. Building a well-connected community is essential to ensure knowledge transfer and exchange across the many actors in Earth System science and HPC, including domain scientists, technology providers, and end users.

Through its CDEP, ESiWACE3 aims to increase its outreach while achieving a more inclusive and diverse community. This includes creating a network of ITCs, by identifying and contacting relevant actors in these countries and sharing technical and communication expertise. The strategy will also promote gender equity by engaging in ongoing activities addressed to women in HPC and empowering female Early Career Scientists (ECSS).

The coordination and support to the ESiWACE3 community is based on three main concepts:

- sustaining and growing the network established in previous ESiWACE phases by providing new opportunities and means for fruitful interactions;
- anchoring the ESiWACE network to ongoing activities to connect the engaged community with other networks (European initiatives, CASTIEL2, CoEs, NCCs, ...);
- promoting training and capacity-building activities across the community.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

The ultimate goal is to promote an active, inclusive, and sustained community, foster the uptake of the project outcomes, and maximise the long-term impact and sustainability of the project and its results.

4.3. Target audiences

In the period since the first version of the CDEP was produced, the main target audiences for ESiWACE3 communications activities have been kept under review. The following broad categories, identified in the stakeholder mapping exercise, undertaken as Milestone M6.1 remain unchanged, except for one:

- scientific community (Earth System modellers)
- HPC community
- training participants
- HPC industry (HPC technologists, technology providers, high-capacity data experts...)
- EuroHPC/EC ecosystem (European digital agenda-related initiatives, CASTIEL2, CoEs, NCCs, ...)
- public authorities such as national meteorological agencies and authorities responsible for climate adaptation
- specialised media

The mapping itself has been updated as further contacts have been identified, and is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Mapping of current and potential stakeholders.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

Interviews have also been conducted with representatives of some of these groups, especially the audiences for training and software services, to better understand their needs. The insights gained from these discussions have been taken into consideration in planning communication about ongoing ESiWACE3 training and services opportunities.

4.4. Planned and completed actions

Communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation are crucial to maximise the project's scientific, economic, and societal impact. The purpose of the activities conducted within this framework is to enhance the visibility of the goals and outcomes of the project and increase awareness of how a new generation of weather and climate models that allow realistic simulations of the Earth System can improve our understanding of weather risks in a changing climate. All project partners contribute to these activities, monitored through target indicators, followed up and updated to maximise their impact.

Communication and dissemination activities and materials are crucial to support the ESiWACE3 project community engagement and to reach all relevant target audiences. Table 1 (from the GA) lists the community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities envisaged in ESiWACE3. Some modifications have been made subsequently to the detailed plans as a result of learning from other projects and from consultation with the different audiences, but overall the intended activities remain unchanged.

Table 1. Outline of community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination activities envisaged in the Grant Agreement.

Table 4: List of community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities planned in ESiWACE3

Type	Activity (target group)	Description and purpose (target indicator)
C	Project website (all)	Maintain and update the existing ESiWACE website, the project's main communication hub, aimed at those involved or interested in the project. It provides the project description, latest news, events, reports, press releases, public deliverables, publications and all the communication materials (>400 visits)
C	Social media (all)	Regular posts will be made to reach a wider community, raise awareness and increase project visibility. We will build on ESiWACE social media accounts (Twitter and YouTube) (>700 followers on Twitter)
C	Communication kit (all)	Set of communication materials, including a brochure, presentation and poster templates, roll-up, and a presentation video (>250 video views)
C	Newsletters (all)	Quarterly project newsletters will be distributed to communicate about the project to the community of interest (people subscribed to the ESiWACE mailing list) (>350 subscribers reached)
C	Press releases (journalists, all)	Press/media releases and briefing materials aimed to generate interest in the project, communicate about events and disseminate results at a local and EU level (2 press releases)
C/D	Videos (all)	The project will produce different types of videos that will help communicate the project objectives, status, and results obtained to various audiences. These may include science explainers, project scientists' biographies, and videos documenting project events. Videos with a selection of the new services developed in WP4 will be created (>200 views/video)
CE	Clustering activities (scientific community, European Digital Agenda, EuroHPC ecosystem)	The project will cluster with other projects and initiatives relevant to HPC for Earth system modelling, such as Destination Earth, other EuroHPC funded COE's and related CSA activities, the ENES ¹⁰ network and national and international projects including NextGEMS, Warm World, ACROSS, MAELSTROM and EXCLAIM (>5 participated activities)
D	Scientific publications (scientific community,	Public project reports and publications in peer-reviewed journals will disseminate key project findings to academic audiences (>20 publications)

Type	Activity (target group)	Description and purpose (target indicator)
	EuroHPC ecosystem)	
CE	Organisation of ENES HPC conference (scientific community, EuroHPC ecosystem)	The organisation of two joint ENES HPC workshop editions (2024 and 2026) will allow a deeper engagement with the project's community of interest (>50 participants/conference)
CE	Activities to reach ITCs, women and ECSs (specific networks)	Individuals and institutions from ITCs will be engaged by sharing technical and communication expertise (>= 5 established contacts) Gender equity will be promoted in the events organised by the project (>20% female participation) Engagement with Early-Career Scientists (ECSs) will give particular attention in the events organised by the project (>40% ECS participation)
D	Slide decks and factsheets (scientific community, HPC technology providers)	Slide decks and factsheets to help disseminate the catalogue of new services created in ESiWACE3 or any other relevant project outcome (>4 services showcased)
CE	Hackathons (scientific community)	Four hackathons to provide hands-on training on ESiWACE3 developments, support the exploitation and sustainability of ESiWACE3 services, and enhance the collaboration within the European modelling community (>80 participants)
CE	Summer schools (ECSs)	Two summer schools targeted at early career scientists to train a new generation of weather and climate modellers to effectively use the latest HPC environments (>60 ECSs)
D	Training materials (scientific community, ECSs)	Teaching material to transfer knowledge on specific project-related topics that will be published online and advertised in relevant platforms to reach a wide audience (>50 downloads)

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

4.4.1. Communication (Task 6.1)

The communication actions aim to reach the project target groups and increase the project visibility. Several communication tools and channels are used to inform target audiences at a local, national, and EU level about the project goals and key messages and maximise the impact of the project communication. These tools and channels include (among others): a revision and update of the existing ESiWACE visual identity; the maintenance, revision, update, and curation of new content of the established [ESiWACE website](#); the social media channels ([Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [YouTube](#)); new communication material (communication kit, videos, infographics, roll-up, etc.); press releases; and quarterly ESiWACE newsletters. Communication materials are made available on the project website and advertised on social media channels.

A range of activities have already been completed, and those are reported here. Forthcoming communication activities and their impact will be reported in further updates of the CDEP (i.e. D6.3 and 6.4). The effectiveness of different communication channels in reaching the target audiences is kept under review, for example by polling participants in training events and workshops about how they became aware of the activities. At the time of writing (month 18), the LinkedIn account has 245 followers, the X (Twitter) account 580 followers, and the YouTube channel 173 subscribers.

Table 2 shows the actions already undertaken and those further actions planned to support the communication of the project. Actions already taken and reported in the first version of the CDEP submitted in Deliverable 6.1, i.e., up to month 6 of the project, are shown in grey.

Table 2. Communication actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Visual identity	Visual identity reviewed: new logo and colour palette created.	-
Communication kit	Templates updated in line with the new visual identity. A range of infographics produced to illustrate the project objectives, services catalogue and training opportunities.	Creation of further new material such as dynamic presentation material that can be displayed on conference stands. Creation of a leaflet and some stickers to promote the project.
Project website	Static website content reviewed and updated to present the new phase of the project. Content updated and augmented regularly.	Restructuring the landing page of the ESiWACE3 website to better present and explain the project (including some of the videos produced within Task 6.4). Restructuring the section covering ESiWACE services to better communicate the offering to potential audiences.
Social media	Existing social media channels from previous phases of the project (Twitter and YouTube) taken over.	Continue to post content.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
	<p>"#MeetESiWACE3Partners" campaign presenting the partners of the ESiWACE3 Consortium</p> <p>New social media channel opened on LinkedIn.</p> <p>Content posted regularly to publicise training opportunities, services calls, and project updates.</p>	
Newsletter	<p>Template for the newsletter updated and first issue released.</p> <p>Further issues released every three months.</p>	Release of further quarterly issues.
Videos	<p>Eight videos presenting the project released on the website.</p> <p>Six videos presenting ESiWACE2 services created, released on the website and YouTube channel, and promoted on the social media channels.</p>	<p>Creation of an animated video to present and better explain the main objectives of the project.</p> <p>Further videos created to present ESiWACE3 services projects, hackathons, summer schools, and scientist bios.</p>
Press releases	-	Press releases to be issued once newsworthy results are available.

4.4.2. Engagement (Tasks 6.2 & 6.3)

Building a well-connected community is essential to ensure knowledge transfer and exchange across the many actors in Earth System science and HPC, including domain scientists, technology providers, and end users. The ESiWACE3 engagement strategy includes creating a network of Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs), promoting gender equity by engaging in ongoing activities addressed to women in HPC, attracting, retaining, and advancing more high-quality female scientific researchers and empowering female Early Career Scientists (ECSs). The aim is to enhance the ESiWACE3 community engagement, mainly focusing on increasing its outreach while achieving a more active, inclusive, gender-balanced, diverse, and sustained community.

Clustering with other European projects and initiatives, in particular through engagement in the activities and networks promoted by CASTIEL2, will also be fostered. Such interactions will ensure links with the European ecosystem of HPC stakeholders and initiatives related to the European digital agenda. The objective is to raise awareness of the project topics and results of interest for the community. Specific actions include the organisation of the joint ENES HPC Workshop editions for 2024 and 2026, the coordination of project requests of HPC resources through the EuroHPC CoE call and the participation of ESiWACE3 in conferences, workshops and events (such as the EGU, ISC, SC, etc.). Information on the participation of ESiWACE3 in such events is collected in an Excel document accessible from the project's wiki.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

In coordination with WP5, videos documenting the training events organised by the project (hackathons, summer schools, etc.) will also be developed and disseminated within the ITCs network. Gender balance amongst presenters and participation of female ECSs will also be considered when promoting the project's events and accepting participants.

Table 3 shows the actions already undertaken and those planned to support the engagement of target communities in the project. Actions already taken and reported in the first version of the CDEP submitted in Deliverable 6.1, i.e., up to month 6 of the project, are shown in grey.

Table 3. Engagement actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Community mailing list	Ongoing management of the community mailing list. Communications circulated to the list regularly.	Further communications issued
Mapping of potential stakeholders	Interviews with relevant participants in ESiWACE3 and the earlier project phases. Surveys of the ESiWACE community (contacts from project mailing lists and social media channels). Interviews with contacts in related projects such as IS-ENES3. Direct approaches to NCC contacts made through the CASTIEL network. Interviews with contacts from partners' professional networks. Trawls of modelling groups through the CORDEX network.	Ongoing follow-up of contacts formed through participation in conferences and other projects.
Participation in conferences/workshops/ events	Coordination of ESiWACE3 participation in annual/biennial events including EuroHPC Summits, European Geosciences Union (EGU) GAs, ISC, Supercomputing, HiPEAC, etc. Participation in scientific workshops run by the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR).	Coordination of participation in future events. Preparation of additional display materials to attract audiences, including dynamic poster displays and videos.
Clustering with other EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs and related initiatives	ESiWACE3 is active in various CASTIEL2-coordinated advisory and technical groups, including the Project Management Technical Group, the HPC CoE Council, training, communication, legacy software and CI/CD taskforces. ESiWACE3 partners also contribute legal support to CASTIEL2, and contribute to the C2ISS and the EuroCC Access portal. Preparation is well advanced for an online training event to be held in collaboration with NCC Austria in September 2024.	Further collaborative training events, hackathons, workshops, webinars, etc.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
	<p>ESiWACE3 is co-organising a conference workshop at PPAM24 with CoEs HiDALGO2, Plasma-PEPSC, BioEXCEL-3, EXCELLERAT, EoCoE and the HANAMI project.</p> <p>ESiWACE3 has submitted a proposal to organise a joint CoE workshop for women in HPC at HiPEAC 2025 in collaboration with MAX, MultiXScale, ChEESE, and POP3.</p>	
Clustering with other projects and initiatives relevant to HPC for earth system modelling	<p>Preparation is well advanced for the first ESiWACE3 summer school, organised in collaboration with the WarmWorld project in Aug/Sep 24.</p> <p>Involvement in the #ClimateResearchNet network for communication for European climate research projects.</p> <p>ESiWACE3 intends to invite representatives of OptimESM, EERIE and Destination Earth to participate in the 3rd General Assembly to be held in November 2024 in Hamburg (Germany).</p>	<p>The second ESiWACE3 summer school will also be a collaboration with WarmWorld.</p> <p>Further collaborative training events, hackathons, workshops, webinars, etc.</p>
Hackathons and summer schools	<p>First hackathon held in Espoo, Finland in October 2023.</p> <p>Second hackathon held in Amsterdam, Netherlands in June 2024.</p> <p>Preparation is well advanced for the first ESiWACE3 summer school to be held in Espoo, Finland in Aug/Sep 24.</p>	Two further hackathons, and a further summer school.
ITCs, women and ECRs	<p>Updating the mapping of potential stakeholders undertaken for M6.1.</p> <p>Mapping of modelling teams in ITCs through contacts with NCCs in ITCs.</p> <p>Participation in the 4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing conference in Riga, Latvia.</p> <p>LinkedIn campaign highlighting ESiWACE3's female researchers for International Women's Day.</p>	<p>Further training events offered online to facilitate participation by researchers from ITCs.</p> <p>Compilation of best-practice guidance for ensuring a diversity-friendly atmosphere at training events and workshops.</p> <p>Increased engagement with climate research networks active in the ITCs, such as the Pannonian Basin Experiment (PANEX).</p> <p>Increased engagement with ECR networks such as the Young Earth Systems Scientists (YESS) community.</p>
ENES HPC workshops	ENES HPC workshop held in Lecce, Italy in May 2024, and associated communication and promotion activities.	Organisation of the next ENES HPC workshop in 2026.
Requests for HPC resources	Coordination of project requests for HPC resources through the EuroHPC calls.	Further coordination of requests through EuroHPC calls.
Interaction with HPC technology providers	Participation in ISC, SuperComputing, HPCKP Annual Meeting, etc.	Further participation in future international and national HPC meetings.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

4.4.3. Dissemination (Task 6.4)

The primary purpose of the project's dissemination activities is to promote the project results and services and their uptake by different communities by delivering relevant and tailored information to the various target audiences in a form that is easy for them to access.

To facilitate dissemination, ESiWACE3 complies with the Open Science policy required by the "Horizon Europe" programme. This policy states mandatory open access to publications, and open science principles are applied throughout the programme. Within this framework, ESiWACE3 is committed to expanding and sustaining the ESiWACE Zenodo Community by adding new open-access publications created within the project. Scientific results are published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at relevant scientific conferences and events. All dissemination materials will be shared through the project communication channels. When relevant, they will be shared at project-related or project-relevant events. ESiWACE3 will also liaise with partner NCCs to make links to training materials available on their websites.

An important element of the project dissemination strategy relies on video materials. First, a series of videos has been produced to help present the project and communicate its objectives and goals. Another set of videos incorporates successful user stories to showcase the services developed in previous phases of ESiWACE. These are all available on the project's YouTube channel. They will be followed by further videos with a selection of new services developed by WP4 to support the preparation of the project's new catalogue of services. Videos documenting project events (e.g. hackathons and summer schools) and project scientists' biographies are also planned. The video strategy will be accordingly adjusted as the project necessities evolve.

Moreover, slide decks will be developed to disseminate further the new services catalogue and other dissemination materials (such as leaflets and factsheets) showcasing the different services or any other relevant project outcome. The compilation of this material, together with the series of videos, will create a portfolio of the services created in ESiWACE3.

Table 4 shows the actions already undertaken and those planned to support dissemination of research outcomes and materials from ESiWACE3. Actions already taken and reported in the first version of the CDEP submitted in Deliverable 6.1, i.e., up to month 6 of the project, are shown in grey.

Table 4. Dissemination actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Videos	Videos presenting the project and its aims. Videos showcasing services delivered in previous phases of the project.	An animated video describing the project for display at conferences, for example. Videos to highlight the portfolio of new services offered in ESiWACE3. Videos documenting training activities such as hackathons and summer schools. Videos profiling ESiWACE3 scientists.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Zenodo community	Take over and update the visual identity of the existing ESiWACE Zenodo community. Ongoing addition of open access publications to the community.	Further open access publications and training materials added to the community.
Scientific publications	Publication of ESiWACE3 results in peer-reviewed journals. Dissemination of results through non-peer-reviewed industry channels such as insidehpc.com.	Further articles in peer-reviewed and other journals.
Services catalogue	Catalogue of topics that might be offered as software services drawn up and issued (D4.1). Infographic promoting the catalogue produced and distributed on the project website and by social media channels.	Further refinement of the description of the catalogue on the project website to clarify the offering.
Software support	Website announcement and promotion on social media of the first call for proposals for software support. Website announcements and promotion on social media of two further calls for proposals. The second of these focuses on support to use tools developed by ESiWACE3 partners. Videos depicting success stories from software support offered in ESiWACE2.	Promotion of a further call for proposals. Videos reporting on the outcomes of ESiWACE3 software support services. Once delivered by CASTIEL 2, adoption of the C2ISS shared platform and Gitrunner to support the diffusion of material and software.
Training events and materials	Publication on the ESiWACE3 website of the project training events calendar. Ongoing publication of relevant events on the training events calendar. Dissemination of workshop training materials through the Zenodo community and through GitHub.	Publication of ESiWACE3 training materials on the project website. Addition of further materials to Zenodo and GitHub.

4.4.4. Exploitation (Task 6.5)

To ensure that the full scientific and societal benefits of the project are realised, the outputs that result from it need to be made openly available and accessible for further research and development by the wider scientific and HPC community and not just by the project partners. But in doing so, intellectual property and related rights issues must be handled correctly. To provide a framework for the exploitation of project results and to ensure that proper knowledge management procedures are followed, an Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP) has been drawn up. This is set out in Appendix 1.

The IPMP provides guidance on the legal framework within which the project's knowledge management takes place. It sets out the respective responsibilities for exploitation within the project, and details the procedures for the identification of exploitable results by partners and their categorisation according to their potential to be exploited.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

Templates for collecting information about results and about any knowledge protection measures planned have been made available to project partners, and will assist them in meeting their obligation to exploit their results during the period for four years after the project has ended.

A range of measures will be adopted by the project to make results available for exploitation, including peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals, dissemination of code and publication of research datasets. A particular focus continues to be sustaining, further developing and expanding the services developed as prototypes in ESiWACE2, and disseminating them to the wider community.

Table 5 shows the actions already undertaken and those planned to support ESiWACE3 exploitation.

Table 5. Exploitation actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Context and legal framework	Defined	
Exploitation guidelines	Defined	
IP Portfolio	Development of supporting tailored material (templates). When necessary, meetings with partners to explain implementation and templates Identification of results and elaboration of the preliminary IP Portfolio.	Follow up of results, updated of the IP portfolio, if needed, and KERs identification
Exploitation	Identification of preliminary exploitation paths.	Exploitation Workshop for discussing appropriate exploitation paths and potential actions to maximise impact.
IP traceability	Under evaluation.	Continuous monitoring.

4.5. Feedback

The effectiveness of the different communications activities described in this plan will be monitored by seeking feedback from participants in training events and workshops, as well as applicants for software support services. Statistics for engagement with the social media channels are also monitored on an ongoing basis. Download statistics for online training materials will be monitored once these materials are live.

5. References

- [Grant agreement](#)
- [Horizon Europe](#)
- [Horizon Europe, open science](#)
- [ESiWACE3 M6.1](#) (2023) Network mapping and engagement strategy
- [ESiWACE3 D6.1](#) (2023) Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (CDEP)

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

- [ESiWACE3 M5.1](#) (2023) Training event calendar
- [ESiWACE3 M4.1](#) (2023) First call for projects in Service 1
- [ESiWACE3 M4.2](#) (2024) First call for projects in Service 2
- [ESiWACE3 M5.2](#) (2023) Report of first hackathon
- [ESiWACE3 D4.1](#) (2023) Initial release of catalogue of expertise and potential service offer
- [ESiWACE3 D7.5](#) (2023) Collaboration plan

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

A major development since the preparation of the first ESiWACE3 CDEP in D6.1 has been the expansion of CASTIEL2's activities in support of coordination of the work of the EuroHPC JU-funded centres of excellence (CoEs). ESiWACE3 is active in several CASTIEL2-organised groups, as well as in the co-organisation with other CoEs of events such as the workshop at the International Conference on Parallel Processing and Applied Mathematics (PPAM24) in September 2024.

At the same time, it is increasingly clear that ESiWACE3 will need to continue to focus effort and resources on domain-specific networks and contacts, to ensure that the training and services that it offers meet the needs of its core audience in the climate and weather modelling community. To be relevant to the target community, the tools and training developed by ESiWACE3 need to reflect the particular context, architecture and requirements of weather and climate modelling, and thus will not all be readily transferable to the audiences for other CoEs or the wider EuroHPC community.

One emerging challenge for the project's aim to promote engagement and participation amongst researchers in the ITCs is in ensuring the accessibility of training to all. The in-person training events - hackathons and summer schools - envisaged in the project proposal were expected to be hosted by ESiWACE3 project partners. But a consequence of this is that they would take place at locations that are geographically remote from the ITC audiences we aim to reach, and feedback has been received that suggests that travel costs are one barrier to participation by ITC (and ECR) researchers. Consideration is therefore being given to options for improving the attractiveness and accessibility of future ESiWACE3 training to these target audiences.

The exploitation section of the CDEP has been much expanded with the incorporation of a separate ESiWACE3 Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP) and report on initial activities. These provide the framework for ensuring the effective exploitation of outcomes from the project as these take shape.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

This deliverable, and the updated CDEP and IPMO that it contains, provide the framework for the dissemination and exploitation of the results and outcomes of ESiWACE3 to the various earth system modelling and HPC communities who can make use of them and build on them in their own development work. It also covers a range of activities aimed at reinforcing the European modelling and HPC communities through strengthened links with other projects and ongoing initiatives at European and national level, such as other EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs, CASTIEL2, the ENES network and model development projects, and is complementary to the ESiWACE3 collaboration plan (ESiWACE3 Deliverable 7.5).

8. Sustainability

Ensuring the sustainability of the results produced during the ESiWACE3 project - and in earlier phases of the project - is the ultimate objective of WP6. This is the goal of the exploitation measures described in sub-section 4.4.4, and it also underpins the communication and dissemination activities.

In working towards the objective, WP6 collaborates closely with other ESiWACE3 work packages. It gives visibility to the software services provided through WP4 which promote the uptake and ongoing use of the tools and methods developed in ESiWACE. It also raises awareness of the training opportunities offered by WP5, which aim to disseminate knowledge and contribute to skills development amongst the target audiences, thus leading to a strengthened and sustainable weather and climate modelling community.

To this end, two workshops about exploitation, sustainability, and impact have been planned, as stated in the GA. The first one will take place during the 3rd ESiWACE3 General Assembly in Hamburg in November 2024. During these events, the partners, through a collective brainstorming exercise led by the exploitation and impact officer, will elaborate potential routes to sustain the exploitation of the CoE and its results during and after the end of the project itself.

The measures described in this deliverable also contribute to a strengthening of the HPC community more generally, through the collaboration and pursuit of synergies with partner projects and initiatives that they involve.

9. Community engagement, dissemination and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

Dissemination of the deliverable will be achieved through:

- publication on the [project website](#);
- depositing it in the [ESiWACE Zenodo community](#).

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

Table 6. Dissemination and engagement activities.

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of people reached
Presentation	PASC	26-28/06/2023 Davos (Switzerland)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/10599997	30
Presentation	NOAA UIFCW	24-28/07/2023 Boulder (USA)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/8366985	30
Workshop	NCAR	09-10/11/2023 Boulder (USA)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10580106 https://zenodo.org/records/10580083	80
Workshop	RSE conference	05/09/2023 Swansea (UK)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10598353	25
Workshop	SuperComputing23	12-17/11/2023 Denver (USA)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/10581020	40-50
Display of video	SuperComputing23	12-17/11/2023 Denver (USA)	HPC community	NA	200
Presentation	Bits&Chips event	10/12/2023 Eindhoven (Netherlands)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10598076	40
Workshop	HiPEAC 2024	17-19/01/2024 Munich (Germany)	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	15
Participation in outreach event	EU Digital Ambassadors	06/03/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	Government representatives and policymakers	Not uploaded yet	10
Poster	EuroHPC Summit	19/03/2024 Antwerp (Belgium)	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12570925	750
Presentation	EuroHPC Summit	21/03/2024 Antwerp (Belgium)	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12570886	750
Training event	FDO Summit training day	19/03/2024 Berlin (Germany)	Scientific community	Not uploaded yet	40
Presentation	FDO Summit	20-21/03/2024 Berlin (Germany)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10960301	150
Presentation	To NCC Netherlands and NCC Italy	02/04/2024 Virtual	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	10

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

Participation in panel discussion	Ocean Decade Conference	08/04/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10953215	30
Display of video	Ocean Decade Conference	10-12/04/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	Scientific community	NA	250
Display of video	4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing Conference	11-12/04/2024 Riga (Latvia)	HPC community	NA	300
Presentation	4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing Conference	11-12/04/2024 Riga (Latvia)	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	300
Presentation	EGU 2024	14-19/04/2024 Vienna (Austria)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/11060523	40
Poster	EGU 2024	14-19/04/2024 Vienna (Austria)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/12570826	100
Presentation	HPCKP annual meeting	08-09/05/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	50
Poster	ISC 2024	12-16/05/2024 Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	100
Presentation	ISC 2024	12-16/05/2024 Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	30
Participation in workshop	Parallel IO NHR workshop	07-08/05/2024 Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community	Not uploaded yet	25
Presentation	Digital Ocean Forum	13/06/2024 Brussels (Belgium)	Scientific community	Not uploaded yet	40

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A

Appendix 1. Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP)

1. Introduction

The purpose of the Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP) is to set out the rules and procedures on how Intellectual Property (IP) matters will be addressed during the project. The current IPMP has been designed for managing the intellectual property that will be used and created within the ESiWACE3 project.

The IPMP has been structured in three main sections as follows:

2 - Context and/or Legal Framework – Introduction to the articles and rules governing the foundations for IPR management.

3 - Action plan/Guidelines – Definition of guidelines or procedure to facilitate the implementation of the IP Management Plan.

4 - IP Portfolio implementation – Results presentation.

At the end of the appendix, an analysis of the general characteristics of the reported results will be made.

2. Context/legal framework

The methodology followed in the IP management plan is based on the commitments made during the signature of the Gant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. To ensure a common understanding about IP management terms, but not only, the main definitions stated in the GA, the Rules of Participation and the CA will apply. These definitions will be completed by those of the European Commission IP Helpdesk¹.

This section an introduction to the articles and rules governing the foundations for IPR management. Most of the information collected within this section comes from the EW3 GA and the EW3 CA, all of them signed by the ESiWACE3 consortium with the conformity of the partners.

2.1 Treatment of confidential information – How and under what conditions confidential information will be shared.

2.2 Background – Additional rights and obligations related to the background (BG) IP, declared BG IP and updates.

2.3 Results – Additional rights and obligations related to the results generated during the project, results collection and procedure to manage their IP.

2.4 Communication/Dissemination – Description of the main requirements that need to be considered before the publication and/or dissemination of the generated results.

2.5 Exploitation paths – Rights and obligations related to the exploitation of the results as well as the main paths for carrying out it.

2.6 Third Party – Entities considered third parties.

2.7 Change of Membership – Impact on the IP rights due to the change of membership in the team.

2.8 TRL – Technology Readiness Levels.

¹https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk/europe-glossary_en.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

2.9 Liability towards each other and dispute resolution – Dispute resolution process.

2.1 Treatment of confidential information

The terms of confidentiality are governed by the article 13 – *Confidentiality and Security*- in the GA

The articles 14 – *Ethics and Values* –, 15 – *Data Protection* – and 16 – *Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) – Background and Results – Access rights and rights of use* – in the GA as well, should be also considered in order to treat the information in a proper way.

All partners are responsible for maintaining confidentiality during implementation of the specific actions and four years after the period set out in Article 16 of the GA (48 months as of 1 January 2023). If a partner requests, the Commission may agree to keep such information confidential for an additional period beyond the initial four years. For more information and to know how this information could be shared to their personnel or third parties check section 10 of the CA.

2.2 Background

Any data, know-how or information – whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results. If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Agreement. According to the Consortium Agreement (section 9.1.2), any Party can add additional Background to Attachment 1 during the Project provided they give written notice to the other Parties. However, approval of the General Assembly is needed should a Party wish to modify or withdraw its Background in Attachment 1.

EW3's Background is governed by the rules stated in the GA and CA. Namely, the following articles should apply:

- Article 16.1 (GA): Background and access rights to background
- Section 9 (CA): Access Rights

The information reflected in the Background will consist of:

- Owner identification
- Background description
- Specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation (Article 16.4 GA & its Annex5)
- Specific restrictions and/or conditions for exploitation (Article 16.4 GA & its Annex5)

2.3 Results

Any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights. Any result generated within the EW3 project will be considered as Results. It includes pieces of information, materials and knowledge and whether or not they can be protected. It includes intellectual property rights (e.g. copyrights, industrial designs, patents...), similar forms of protection (e.g. rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g. confidential material).

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

EW3's Results are governed by the rules stated in the Grant Agreement, and Consortium Agreement. Namely, the following articles should apply:

- Article 16.2 (GA): Ownership of results
- Article 16.4 (GA): Specific rules on IPR, results and background

These rules are also collected in the CA under section 8 – *Results* - and section 9 – *Access Rights*.

For a proper management of the Results generated within EW3, the following issues must be identified:

- (1) Identification of the results, description and application.
- (2) Type of results (Software, Hardware, Know-how, System...).
- (3) Ownership.
- (4) Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and, if applies, other possible metrics such as Market Readiness Level (MRL), Social Technology Readiness Level (STRL), etc.
- (5) IPR protection strategy.
- (6) Third parties IP dependencies.
- (7) Access conditions.
- (8) Key exploitable results.
- (9) Exploitation strategy.

2.4 Communication/dissemination

The communication and dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, is governed by the procedure of Article 17 of the GA subject to the provisions stated in section 8.4 of the CA (contact the WP6 Leader (BSC) in case of doubts; rosa.rodriquez@bsc.es).

2.5 Exploitation paths

The use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

The objective of the exploitation activities is to transform the results of the project into concrete benefits. In many sectors, protecting intellectual property, e.g. by filing patent applications, provides a basis for exploitation, including through licensing results. This can form part of a marketing strategy, but not only.

At project level, exploitation activities promote:

- The use of results in developing, creating and marketing a product or process;
- Or in creating and providing a service;
- Or in standardisation activities;
- Or in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned leading to the aforementioned exploitation.

Hence, exploitation activities can pave the way to different tangible and intangible benefits such as:

- Creating sovereign world-class champions in industry, services and research;
- Gain market share and create innovation-based GDP;

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

- Provide our public and private researchers with climate and weather tools way ahead of market to the latest products and technologies (key R&D IP breakthroughs are usually 4-5 years ahead of mass availability);
- Attracting new talent;
- Providing international and interdisciplinary collaboration opportunities;
- Improving access to other funding prospects;
- Generating new sources of income;
- Contributing to societal goals;
- Generating policy impact, improving current and/or help shaping future legislation.

EW3 partners must – up to four years after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1) – use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing according Article 16 of the GA (48 months as of 1 January 2023). Common tools towards these direction are (i) patent publications; (ii) establishment of spin-off or start-up companies; (iii) license practices (proprietary, open-source); and (iv) use of the results for academic purposes (trainings, curriculum implementation, PhD thesis, etc.).

Additional information regarding exploitation clauses in EW3 can be found in Annex 5 from GA article 16 and section 9 from CA.

2.6 Third party

Third Party means any entity (whether Affiliated Entity or other Participant) which is not a signatory to the CA (Consortium Agreement 1.2 Additional Definitions).

2.7 Change of membership

A non-defaulting Party leaving voluntarily and with the other Parties' consent shall have Access Rights to the Results developed until the date of the termination of its participation, section 9.7 of the CA. A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the project or, in the case of Section 9.7.2.1.2 of the CA, after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

In case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights shall cease immediately upon receipt by the Defaulting Party of the formal notice of the decision of the General Assembly to terminate its participation in the consortium.

2.8 Technology Readiness Levels (TRL)

Where a topic description refers to a TRL, the following definitions apply, unless otherwise specified:

- TRL 1 – Basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – Technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – Experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 – Technology validated in lab
- TRL 5 – Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – System prototype demonstration in operational environment

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

- TRL 8 – System complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

2.9 Liability towards each other and dispute resolution

Respect of any information or materials (including Results and Background) supplied by one Party to another under the Project, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to the sufficiency or fitness for purpose nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties. Therefore,

- the recipient Party shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials, and
- no Party granting Access Rights shall be liable in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from any other Party (or its entities under the same control) exercising its Access Rights.

See section 5 – Liability towards each other - of the CA for more details.

Dispute settlement is governed by the Article 33 – Damages - stated in the GA and section 11.8 –Settlement of disputes – of the CA.

Applicable law and settlement of disputes shall survive the expiration or termination of the Consortium Agreement as stated in section 3.3 of the CA.

Additionally, other more binding liabilities could be addressed in bipartite exploitation agreement to complete the consortium agreements.

3. Action plan

The IPMP guideline has been designed with the aim of establishing a clear procedure to facilitate the implementation of the IPMP. Next steps indicate which activities and by who need to be carried out to fulfill it.

3.1 Setting Definitions

The IP Management Task Leader (BSC), hereinafter IPM, will be the responsible for compiling the more relevant definitions, including those mentioned in the CA and the GA, related to the IP management of the project. These definitions have been already included in Annex 1, at the end of the document to facilitate access.

3.2 Background management

Background is defined in the CA as any data, know-how or information—whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights—that is: (a) held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement, and (b) needed to implement the action or exploit the results. If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Agreement. Should partner see the need to add elements to the background, they should contact the IPM and the ESiWACE Project Manager (BSC) to initiate the process.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

3.3 Identification of Results

The Results will be identified and defined by each partner, supported by the IPM (BSC), who will facilitate additional materials such as templates or presentations for collecting the Results and compile the project's *IP Portfolio*.

Three levels of Results will be considered:

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC1:
EPI2 Results level classification

- *KERs (Key Exploitable Results)* - An identified main interesting result which has been **selected and prioritised**, by the consortium, due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.
- *Main Results* – An identified main interesting result, by the partner(s), with potential for exploitation but not at KER level.
- *Results* - Any tangible (e.g., prototypes) or intangible output (e.g., know how, formulas) of the action, such as data, knowledge, and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action, as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.

This pyramidal approach or classification of results relies on a bottom-up approach built on the general Results of the project (pyramidal base) that each partner will identify. From these Results, when the development of the project allows it, each owner should identify the Main Results. Finally, from the latter, during the first exploitation Workshop, the KERs should be selected and prioritised, at consortium level, according to the high potential for exploitation based on market impact, contribution to societal goals, and/or potential for policy or standard establishment.

For that purpose, a template, has been shared in the internal EW3 share point by the IPM (BSC) with the partners. Every partner have access to the template and is responsible for filling it in. The IPM will support this action and will follow up it to check if it is being carried out or not.

These templates will be alive documents that should reflect the evolution of the results during the project.

The initial template reflects different concepts that allow the identification and monitoring of the result in order to guide and, if necessary, recommend actions and ways to exploit the result. This first table has been synthesised in order to gather the most interesting information taking into account the state and evolution of the project. The following concepts are shown in this table:

- (1) Work Package in which the component (result) is developed and/or described.
- (2) Result identification: Name, type (Software, Hardware, Know-how, System) and classification (Result, Main Result).
- (3) Expected TRL. Along the project, updated versions of the template could also include MRL and/or SRL indicators if considered applicable.
- (4) Ownership.
- (5) IP Traceability and protection.
- (6) Expected IPR.
- (7) Expected exploitation strategy.
- (8) Current status.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

(9) Related projects.

Note, the template can be updated during the project depending on the necessities.

Regarding IP protection (point 5), each of the partners is responsible for selecting the most appropriate protection mechanisms for its results, according to its individual exploitation strategy. In case of indecision, the IPM will assess the possible protection mechanisms to help partners choose the most appropriate one.

In addition to the day-to-day management of IP issues, once per year, the IPM (BSC) will present a progress report, including the updated EW3's Results IP, which corresponds to deliverables D6.2, D6.3 and D6.5 - *Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP), Report of activities and First/Second update of the CDEP, and Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan* respectively.

In order to track, but also to crosscheck the results, permanent communication among the IPM (BSC) and the partners is expected.

3.4 Identification of Exploitation paths

All the partners have the obligation to exploit their project results up to four years after the end of the project (2.2.4 GA). A preliminary exploitation plan has been carried out as part of Task 6.5 by the IPM (BSC), supported by the partners, and presented in deliverable D6.1. Updated plans according to the progress and emerging results of the project will be performed and reflected in the corresponding CDEPs as defined in WP6. This information, extended as well to the general Results, will be also collected in the IP Portfolio.

4. IP portfolio implementation

This section compiles the background updates, if there were, and the Results declared by the partners during the current reporting period (M18). This preliminary information will be updated and complemented progressively in each corresponding deliverable (D6.3 and D6.5, due in M36 and M47, respectively). The main objective of this preliminary IP portfolio is to gather and present the Results produced within the project, identify their ownership, the strategy for protecting the IP and the strategy for exploitation. Note that the strategy for exploitation is focused on individual Results, and not addressing or mentioning possible agreements reached, or under discussion, between partners. In addition, the IP portfolio will consider IP traceability to identify any possible issue that could prevent the use of the Result outside the project, will reflect the status of the Result during the reporting period, including as well the "current TRL" and the expected TRL at the end of the project. As the project moves forward, additional information as for example MRL (Market Readiness Level) will be considered.

For this deliverable a first identification of results has been carried out. A bottom-up approach is applied, therefore the present deliverable will focus on the identification of the Results and Main Results to build a complete IP Portfolio and in the next deliverable the identification of the Key Exploitable Results will be prioritised.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

The Results are presented by partners according to the following structure. An initial table summarize the Results generated by the partner and then individual tables show the information of the corresponding Result.

4.1 Individual results

ATOS -----

ATOS has not generated any individual results for the moment.

ATOS has declared joint results.

BSC -----

Table 1: BSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS					
RESULT		Brief description		Classification	WP
1	AUTO-RPE	Tools to reduce the precision of the variable model automatically from double to single		Main result	2
2	AUTO-Profile	Tools to analyse the computational performance of an application automatically		Main result	2
3	HPCW Risc-V version	Ported version to RISC-V Linux of the HPCW suite		Result	1

1 AUTO-RPE							Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	BSC	
			Current	4			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Provider Other 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Portability improved				
Related projects			-				

2 AUTO-Profile							Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	BSC	
			Current	2			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Provider Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Proof of concept				
Related projects			-				

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

3 HPCW Risc-V version						Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	BSC
			Current	2		
IP	Traceability	Dependencies with LLVM toolchain and RISC-V Linux components under open source licence and HPCW component licences				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 			
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative Research 			
Current status (M18) of the Result			Establishing the required technology to execute the result			
Related projects			ESiWACE-2, EPI SGA1, EW3, EUPILOT			

CMCC -----

Table 2: CMCC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1 Ophidia accessing Zarr format	Prototype extension of Ophidia HPDA framework for supporting Zarr data format. This will allow applying data analytics on a data format which is gaining more traction in the community	Result	3
2 NEMO on GPU	NEMO porting and integration on MN5 and LUMI	Main result	2
3 PSyclone	Use of PSyclone in the NEMO build system.	Main result	2

1 Ophidia accessing Zarr format						Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	CMCC
			Current	4		
IP	Traceability	Several dependencies on open source libraries/tools, starting from NetCDF NCZarr				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 			
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 			
Current status (M18) of the Result			Preliminary integration completed, currently testing with different datasets and infrastructures			
Related projects			-			

2 NEMO on GPU						Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	CMCC
			Current	3		
IP	Traceability	-				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and marketing a product or process Further Research activities 			
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 			
Current status (M18) of the Result			proof of concept			
Related projects			-			

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

3	PSyclone						Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	CMCC	
			Current	4			
IP	Traceability	Based on open source license					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			Integration of the PSyclone to compile GPU-enabled version of NEMO for Med24 and GLOB16 configuration				
Related projects			-				

CSC -----

CSC has not generated any individual results for the moment.
 CSC has declared joint results.

DKRZ -----

Table 3: DKRZ – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
	RESULT	Brief description	Classification
1	FDO4Climate: Initial Evaluation	Evaluation of the readiness of published climate simulation output for automated analysis.	Main result
			WP
			3

1	FDO4Climate: Initial Evaluation						Main result
Type	SCI	TRL	Expected	4	Ownership	DKRZ	
			Current	4			
IP	Traceability	Own background					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Permissive Collaborative Research Participation in relevant forums/ standardization groups, etc. 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			Milestone M3.1 finished, the result was the topic of that milestone. Current work continues along the recommendations laid out in M3.1				
Related projects			-				

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

ECMWF -----

Table 4: ECMWF – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Field Compression Library	It can be used by scientific groups to explore data compression for weather and climate science	Main result	3
2	FVM	New dynamical core of ECMWF that will be used for operational weather predictions and climate simulations.	Main result	2

1							Main result
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	ECMWF
				Current	5		
	IP	Traceability	-				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and marketing a product or process 				
		Route/s	-				
	Current status (M18) of the Result				Development in progress		
Related projects				-			

2							Main result
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	ECMWF
				Current	5		
	IP	Traceability	-				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	-				
	Current status (M18) of the Result				Development in progress		
Related projects				-			

JSC -----

Table 5: JSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Training Calendar	Collecting and publishing domain-specific activities such as ESM user forums, workshops, and summer schools on topics of computational and data sciences as well as high performance computing	Result	5

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

1 Training Calendar						Result
Type	EVENT	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	JSC
			Current	N/A		
IP	Traceability	-				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 			
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education/ Training activities 			
Current status (M18) of the Result			online training calendar has been created and integrated in ESiWACE web site			
Related projects			-			

LT -----

LT has not generated any individual results for the moment.

LT contributes mostly to actions to maximise impact. Not expected to generate any significant results.

MPI-M -----

MPI-M has not generated any individual results for the moment.

MPI-M has declared joint results.

NLESC -----

Table 6: NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
	RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Energy-Efficient GPU Computing SC23 tutorial	Training researchers and practitioners how to use improve the energy efficiency of their GPU applications. Demonstrating how to use Kernel Tuner and Kernel Float to this end.	Result	2&4
2	Kernel Float	Kernel Float is a header-only library for CUDA that simplifies working with vector types and reduced precision floating-point arithmetic in GPU code.	Main result	1
3	Kernel Tuner	Software development tool for automatic performance tuning, automated testing, balancing computational efficiency, energy efficiency, and/or accuracy on GPUs	Main result	2

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

1	Energy-Efficient GPU Computing SC23 tutorial						Result
Type	METH	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	NLESC	
			Current	N/A			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Permissive 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			Material has been created and tutorial given at SC23.				
Related projects			-				

2	Kernel Float						Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	2	Ownership	NLESC	
			Current	2			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Permissive 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			Library has been created, currently being further tested and refined				
Related projects			-				

3	Kernel Tuner						Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	NLESC	
			Current	5			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Permissive 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			New features have been added to support accuracy tuning, will need more refinement and testing				
Related projects			-				

SMHI -----

SMHI has not generated any individual results for the moment.
 SMHI has declared joint results.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

UH -----

Table 7: UH – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Cartopy-Pyodide	Port Cartopy to work inside Pyodide and to contribute it to the Pyodide project such that Cartopy can now be used in Pyodide environments by anyone.	Result	3
2	Field Compression Benchmark Suite	This will allow anyone to reproduce the results produced by the test suite in HPC using the online compression lab without the need to access an HPC system.	Main result	3
3	NetCDF-Pyodide	Our contribution is to port NetCDF to work inside Pyodide and to contribute it to the Pyodide project such that NetCDF can now be used in Pyodide environments by anyone.	Result	2
4	Online Field Compression Laboratory Prototype V1	The online field compression laboratory builds on ECMWF's field compression library to work in a WebAssembly-based Python JupyterLite environment (Pyodide) that allows researchers to explore data compression for weather and climate data in a reproducible environment in their web browser without needing to install anything.	Main result	3

1 Cartopy-Pyodide							Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	UH	
			Current	6			
IP	Traceability						
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			Cartopy is now provided as an available-by-default package in Pyodide				
Related projects			-				

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

2 Field Compression Benchmark Suite							Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	UH	
			Current	3			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source – Permissive • Participation in relevant forums/ groups... 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Development of the benchmark suite has been paused since November 2023 due to parental leave, and will resume once the Compression Hackathon paper has been submitted. At this time, the benchmark suite can benchmark the performance and goodness across the variables and dimensions of a variety of datasets in NetCDF, Zarr, or GRIB format.				
Related projects			-				

3 NetCDF-Pyodide							Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	UH	
			Current	6			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			NetCDF4 is now provided as an available-by-default package in Pyodide				
Related projects			-				

4 Online Field Compression Laboratory Prototype V1							Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	UH	
			Current	3			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service • Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source – Copyleft • Education/ Training activities • Collaborative Research • Service Provider 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Development of the online compression lab has continued and is now targeting the release of a fully-working prototype with several demo Jupyter notebooks exploring compression in a reproducible online environment.				
Related projects			-				

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

4.2 Joint and Multiple results

ATOS / DKRZ -----

Table 8: ATOS/DKRZ – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
1 HCPW	HPC Weather benchmarking suite. HPCW isolates key elements in the workflow of weather and climate prediction systems to improve performance and to allow a detailed performance comparison for different hardware platforms thus fostering co-design with vendors and technology providers		Main Result	1

1 HCPW						Main Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	ATOS & DKRZ
			Current	5		
IP	Traceability	Open source licence components developed outside the project (ICON; IFS Dwarfs: ecTrans, ecRad, dwarf-p-cloudsc; NEMO) are used, agreements with the owners are in place.				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Permissive 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Development towards version 3 release			
Related projects			ESCAPE-2, ESiWACE2 and potential others (EPI-SGA2, EMOPASS)			

BSC / SMHI -----

Table 9: BSC/SMHI – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
1 Docker EC-EARTH	Containerization of the code EC-EARTH for running climate simulation (comes from AUTOSUBMIT WF manager and EC-EARTH)		Main result	1

1 Docker EC-EARTH						Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	BSC, SMHI
			Current	3		
IP	Traceability	-				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and marketing a product or process Further Research activities 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Proof of concept			
Related projects			-			

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

CSC / UH / ATOS / DKRZ / JSC -----

Table 10: CSC/UH/ATOS/DKRZ/JSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Summer School 2024	Training of Early Career Scientists in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use the latest HPC environments	Result 5
2	Summer School 2025	Training of Early Career Scientists in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use the latest HPC environments	Result 5

1 Summer School 2024						Result
Type	EVENT	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	CSC, UH, ATOS, DKRZ, JSC
			Current	N/A		
IP	Traceability	-				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education/ Training activities Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Development of training material has begun			
Related projects			Possibility in AI4PEX			

2 Summer School 2025						Result
Type	EVENT	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	CSC, UH, ATOS, DKRZ, JSC
			Current	N/A		
IP	Traceability	-				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education/ Training activities Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Pending summer school 2024 to begin			
Related projects			Possibility in AI4PEX			

DKRZ / MPI -----

Table 11: DKRZ/MPI – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1	ICON-HPCW	This is the application of an existing code (the Climate and Weather Model ICON. NOT developed by ESiWACE3) within the HPCW Benchmark suite.	Result 1

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

2							ICON-HPCW		Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	8	Ownership	DKRZ, MPI			
			Current	4					
IP	Traceability	ICON is co-developed by several institutions. It is open source and is being used as a component of the HPCW benchmark suite.							
	Protection	Copyright							
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 							
	Route/s	-							
Current status (M18) of the Result			A version of ICON included into HPCW as proof of concept						
Related projects			potentially HANAMI						

JSC / BSC / CSC / ATOS -----

Table 12: JSC/BSC/CSC/ATOS – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Software Stack	Review and consolidate the software stack for ESM applications	Result

1							Software Stack		Result
Type	PROD	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	JSC, BSC, CSC, ATOS			
			Current	N/A					
IP	Traceability	-							
	Protection	Copyright							
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization activities 							
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Provider 							
Current status (M18) of the Result			consolidated list of ESM software stack has been prepared						
Related projects			-						

MPI-M / DKRZ / BSC / ECMWF -----

Table 13: MPI-M/DKRZ/BSC/ECMWF – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1	Efficient data layouts for ESM output	Data layouts for fast ingestion, cataloguing, distribution and retrieval	Result

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

1 Efficient data layouts for ESM output							Result
Type	METH	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	MPI-M, DKRZ, BSC, ECMWF	
			Current	3			
IP	Traceability	Based on open source					
	Protection	Development in progress					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft Licensing - Open Source - Permissive Collaborative Research 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Exploration of available concepts				
Related projects			WarmWorld				

NLESC / BSC / DKRZ / NLESC / ATOS -----

Table 14: NLESC/BSC/DKRZ/NLESC/ATOS – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1 ESiWACE3 Service 1	Service 1 creates small collaborative projects between ESiWACE3 partners and researchers in weather and climate to provide guidance, assistance, and training to help researchers with porting and optimising their weather and climate simulations for modern HPC systems.	Result	4

1 ESiWACE3 Service 1							Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	NLESC, BSC, DKRZ, NLESC, ATOS	
			Current	N/A			
IP	Traceability	-					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	-				
Current status (M18) of the Result			Service has been created and is up and running				
Related projects			-				

SMHI / BSC / NLESC -----

Table 15: SMHI/BSC/NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1 EC-Earth4	Porting/integration on LUMI and national systems	Result	1

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

1 EC-Earth4							Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	SMHI, BSC, NLeSC	
			Current	3			
IP	Traceability	Based on open source					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative Research 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			prototype developed				
Related projects			-				

SMHI / NLeSC / ATOS / DKRZ / BSC -----

Table 16: SMHI/NLeSC/ATOS/DKRZ/BSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1 Service catalogue	Collection of partner expertise and specific service offers for the public	Result	2

1 Service catalogue							Result
Type	DOC	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	SMHI, NLeSC, ATOS, DKRZ, BSC	
			Current	N/A			
IP	Traceability	Own background					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative Research 					
Current status (M18) of the Result			Published on ESiWACE3 website				
Related projects			-				

UH / NLeSC -----

Table 17: UH/NLeSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
1 Compression-Hackathon	This result could be used to drastically lower the storage and data transfer costs for model restart states.	Main result	3

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.2

1	Compression-Hackathon					Main result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	3	Ownership	UH, NLESC
			Current	3		
IP	Traceability	-				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source – Permissive • Collaborative Research 				
Current status (M18) of the Result			The hackathon results are published. A subsequent research project that significantly expanded the exploration of lossy compression of model states is nearing completing and will result in the publication of a paper.			
Related projects			-			

5. Analysis

The IP management plan for EW3 and the corresponding guidelines for its implementation have been presented in this document. As part of the implementation, the initial Results/IP portfolio has been also presented.

Up to 25 Results have been identified. More than 80% of the Results will contribute to extend the open source community including open source hardware, and up to 20% will contribute to increase the HPC portfolio of the partners. Almost all the Results will contribute for further research activities to continue developing forefront European technologies and will promote international and interdisciplinary collaboration opportunities.